

Building Interreligious Dialogue in the Urban Parish Based on Hans Küng's Theory of Dialogue

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Abstract: Religious diversity in Malang City often triggers conflict and tension in religious life. Therefore, interreligious dialog is important to build as an effort to create harmony and tolerance between religious communities. The Forum for Communication Among Religious Communities (FKAUB) is an important forum for promoting interreligious dialog. FKAUB consistently holds regular meetings between religious leaders from various communities. These meetings provide a venue for discussion and dialogue on sensitive issues or potential conflicts in the community. FKAUB also plays a role in educating the community about the importance of tolerance. The presence of FKAUB in Malang City has become an inspiring example for the wider community, that interfaith dialog and cooperation is the main key in building a peaceful and harmonious coexisting society. Based on the research on the contribution of FKAUB in building interreligious dialog in urban parishes, the researcher used Hans Küng's theoretical study. Hans Küng's dialogue theory emphasizes the similarity of essential values in each religion. By realizing the similarity of these essential values, it can be an effort to build public awareness of the similarity of moral values which is the basis for fostering tolerance and harmony between religious communities.

INTRODUCTION

The activity among religious communities is a relevant religious practice in Indonesia, which has a multicultural environment in terms of religion. The presence of religions has an impact on the religious life in the city of Malang. One prominent aspect of religious life in Malang is the diversity of religions. Islam is the majority religion in the city, with a significant portion of the population identifying themselves as Muslims. However, religious diversity is also evident with Christian churches, Hindu temples, and Buddhist viharas scattered throughout the city (Kholish and Rohmah, 2020). This creates a unique atmosphere where various religions and beliefs coexist peacefully. However, there are still individuals who often disrupt the harmony in religious life in Malang.

One phenomenon of intolerance in religious life in Malang is the rejection of the local community towards the worship activities of the Catholic community in the Landungsari area of Malang. As a result, the Catholic community in that area faces difficulties in finding a place to conduct worship and spiritual activities. This intolerance in Malang undermines the unity

among religious communities. Therefore, the existence of such a phenomenon highlights the importance of building interreligious dialogue.

Interreligious dialogue has become an interesting theme lately. It involves different religions coming together to foster a spirit of tolerance in the country. Interreligious dialogue acts as a bridge in society, connecting individuals or groups representing various religions and beliefs with the aim of understanding the differences and similarities among the beliefs of religious communities (Kristiawan, 2020). Building interreligious dialogue requires understanding among religious communities about differences that often trigger conflicts and tensions in religious life. Interreligious dialogue opens the door to exchanging ideas, strengthening mutual respect, and promoting tolerance for differences (Sihombing, 2020). It also plays a role in creating peace and stability in community life, preventing the escalation of religious conflicts and promoting reconciliation amidst tensions (Muhtadi, 2019).

The Forum for Communication Among Religious Communities (FKAUB) serves as an important platform for promoting interreligious dialogue (cf., Kholish and Rohmah, 2020). FKAUB has consistently organized regular meetings between religious leaders from various communities. These meetings provide a space for discussing sensitive issues or potential conflicts within the community that can be addressed through open dialogue and active listening. With an atmosphere filled with mutual respect, religious leaders can understand each other's perspectives and seek common ground for problem resolution without disrupting social harmony (Kristiawan, 2020).

In addition, FKAUB plays a crucial role in educating the public about the importance of tolerance. Through the dissemination of accurate and inspirational information, FKAUB strives to build a broader understanding of religious diversity and the importance of respecting differences. In doing so, society can gain a deeper understanding of diversity and the importance of maintaining peace and harmony.

The pinnacle of the interreligious dialogue concept in FKAUB is the establishment of relationships based on mutual respect, trust, and cooperation among religious communities. The awareness of the importance of respecting differences in beliefs forms the basis for inclusive and harmonious relationships between religions. FKAUB's success in maintaining harmony and addressing potential conflicts between religions serves as an inspirational example for the broader community, emphasizing that dialogue and cooperation among religious communities are key to building a peaceful and harmonious coexistence. FKAUB's presence in Malang is not just an organization but an important concept that holds deep meaning for religious and national life in Indonesia. The organization was formed in response to various conflicts among religious communities that often occurred in Indonesia. FKAUB is an initiative to strengthen cooperation between various religious leaders and community figures in building constructive interreligious dialogue. FKAUB is an independent organization not tied to any government entity, and it has played a significant role in maintaining harmony among religious communities in Indonesia.

The primary mission of FKAUB is to promote tolerance among religious communities. In this diverse environment, FKAUB strives to encourage individuals to better understand and respect the beliefs of others (Prayuda et al., 2019). FKAUB facilitates interfaith activities aimed at creating a tolerant order within society.

In building interreligious dialogue in urban parishes, particularly in Malang, FKAUB also plays a crucial role in fostering interreligious dialogue. Malang has religious diversity, which is a characteristic of religious life in the city. Islam is the majority religion, with most of the population identifying themselves as Muslims. However, religious diversity is also visible with numerous Christian churches, Hindu temples, and viharas that have become icons in Malang. Nevertheless, there are still individuals who often disrupt harmony in religious life in Malang. One phenomenon of religious intolerance in Malang is the rejection of the local community towards the worship activities of the Catholic community in the Landungsari area, Malang. As a result, the Catholic community in that area faces difficulties in finding a place for worship. What does FKAUB in Malang do? In reality, FKAUB's participation in resolving the Landungsari case is not yet evident, but efforts to dialogue and bring together the conflicting parties have been made as an attempt to find a constructive solution to the conflict.

Additionally, FKAUB is active in organizing social activities together, such as social service, fundraising for charity, and other humanitarian activities involving participation from various religious communities. For example, during the eruption of Mount Semeru, FKAUB, along with religious leaders, conducted social service by channeling contributions in the form of money, basic necessities, etc. Through such collaborations, FKAUB has strengthened solidarity among religious communities in Malang, demonstrating that interfaith cooperation can have a significant positive impact on society.

The presence of FKAUB in Malang can be an agent for realizing peace and tolerance among religious communities (cf., Kholish and Rohmah, 2020). Therefore, FKAUB needs to prioritize interreligious dialogue as an effort to build harmony and stability in Malang. FKAUB's contribution to interreligious dialogue builds strong relationships among religious communities and helps overcome misconceptions or prejudices that may exist among religious communities by providing better insights into the teachings and practices of various religions (Firdaus, 2014).

METHOD

In the research on the Contribution of FKAUB in Building Interreligious Dialogue in Urban Parishes (A Study based on Hans Küng's dialogue theory), the researcher used a qualitative research method by collecting data through interviews. Qualitative approach is a research method aimed at understanding social phenomena or human behavior through the collection, analysis, and interpretation of non-numeric data (Gunawan, 2013). Qualitative research often involves data collection techniques such as interviews, observations, and content analysis (Gunawan, 2013). This method allows researchers to gain in-depth and comprehensive insights into the perspectives, motivations, and contexts that shape a particular phenomenon.

The interview data will be analyzed using Hans Küng's dialogue theory as a guide to evaluate the effectiveness of the dialogue conducted by FKAUB.

In the study on the contribution of FKAUB in building interreligious dialogue in urban parishes, the researcher selected the research location at the Parish of Maria Diangkat Ke Surga, Malang Diocese, with research subjects being the parishioners of Maria Diangkat Ke Surga, Lely. Data collection will be carried out through interview methods. The interview data will be analyzed using Hans Küng's dialogue theory as a guide to evaluate the effectiveness of the dialogue conducted by FKAUB. After analyzing the data, the researcher will interpret the research findings to see the extent of FKAUB's contribution in building interreligious dialogue in the urban parish. After finding the findings from the data analysis, the researcher will present a conclusion based on the research findings and recommendations on how to strengthen FKAUB's contribution in building interreligious dialogue based on Hans Küng's dialogue theory. The following are the interview instruments:

Introduction to the congregation about FKAUB

1. Do you know what FKAUB is?
2. Are you aware of the role of FKAUB?
3. In your opinion, is FKAUB known by the parishioners in the parish?

Catholic congregants' perceptions of FKAUB'S role in facilitating interreligious dialogue in the parish

1. How do you perceive FKAUB's role in facilitating interreligious dialogue in this parish?
2. In your opinion, how does FKAUB strengthen relationships among religious communities in this parish?
3. Do you think FKAUB has changed your perception of the importance of religious tolerance in the community around the parish?
4. Have you felt any changes in how Catholic parishioners interact with people of other religions since FKAUB became active in this parish? If yes, what are those changes?
5. In your opinion, has FKAUB succeeded in building a better understanding between Catholic parishioners and people of other religions through interreligious dialogue?

Catholic congregants' level of understanding of FKAUB'S role in promoting religious tolerance among the parishioners

1. In your opinion, has FKAUB successfully addressed religious issues that often lead to conflicts?
2. Do you feel an increase in understanding of religious tolerance among religious communities thanks to FKAUB?
3. How do you evaluate FKAUB's efforts in teaching specific and effective values of religious tolerance to Catholic parishioners in our parish?
4. How does FKAUB communicate with Catholic parishioners to provide a better understanding of the importance of religious tolerance in our society?

Catholic congregants' views on FKAUB'S efforts in overcoming stereotypes or negative prejudices against catholic parishioners

1. In your opinion, has FKAUB successfully overcome stereotypes or negative prejudices against Catholic parishioners in our community? If yes, how were these efforts carried out?
2. Do you think Catholic parishioners feel a change in the community's attitude towards them after engaging with FKAUB in efforts to overcome stereotypes?
3. Do you have personal experiences showing the positive impact of FKAUB's efforts in overcoming stereotypes or negative prejudices against Catholic parishioners in our parish?
4. Do you feel that FKAUB has successfully created a safe and open space for Catholics?
5. Do you have any specific recommendations you would like to give to FKAUB in their efforts to overcome stereotypes or negative prejudices against Catholic parishioners?

Assessment of catholic congregants on the effectiveness of FKAUB in building interreligious dialogue as an effort to strengthen relationships between catholic parishioners and people of other religions

1. Do you have concrete experiences showing positive changes in the relationship between Catholic parishioners and people of other religions after participating in interreligious dialogue led by FKAUB?
2. What is your opinion on these activities?
3. Are there specific activities or programs by FKAUB that you think have been most successful in strengthening relationships between Catholic parishioners and people of other religions through interreligious dialogue?
4. What recommendations do you have for FKAUB in promoting interreligious dialogue?

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In interviews with four key respondents, namely Mrs. Nunik, Mr. Ramadi, Mr. Edy, and Mr. Petrus in the parish of Maria Diangkat Ke Surga Lely, various aspects were revealed regarding the community's awareness of the Interreligious Communication Forum (FKAUB) and its role in facilitating interfaith dialogue, promoting religious tolerance, and addressing stereotypes or negative prejudices against Catholic believers in the Lely Parish. In response to the first question about the community's awareness of FKAUB, Mrs. Nunik stated that FKAUB is well-known among the community in the Lely Parish. Mr. Ramadi emphasized that the community is familiar with FKAUB, although there may be some confusion with FKUB. Mr. Edy mentioned that many believers recognize FKAUB because Father Eko Atmono is the coordinator of FKAUB in the Lely Parish. Mr. Petrus stated that FKAUB has become part of the familiarity within the community. Considering the interview results, the community's awareness of FKAUB is relatively high, but there is a need for special attention to differentiate it from FKUB to avoid confusion.

The Interreligious Communication Forum (FKAUB) serves as the frontline in facilitating interfaith dialogue in the Lely Parish. In its efforts to strengthen diversity and weave bonds among believers of different faiths, FKAUB has proven itself not only known but also relied upon in promoting tolerance and understanding among the congregation. FKAUB, as a

platform for dialogue, plays a crucial role in opening the door to interfaith communication in the Lely Parish. Through diverse activities such as seminars, group discussions, and social events, FKAUB creates a safe and open space where believers from various religious backgrounds can gather, converse, and understand each other. A key aspect of its function is to build a deeper understanding of the values of each religion.

In interviews with key respondents such as Mrs. Nunik, Mr. Ramadi, Mr. Edy, and Mr. Petrus, it was revealed that FKAUB has played a central role in educating the believers of the Lely Parish about religious diversity. Mrs. Nunik, for example, described how FKAUB actively facilitates interfaith dialogue through various activities, enriching the perspectives of believers on the diversity of beliefs. Mrs. Nunik said, "with the presence of FKAUB, believers are strengthened in building relationships between believers of different faiths, and we are now working on building tolerance within the WKRI (Religious Harmony Forum)" (Nunik, 2023). It is important to acknowledge that FKAUB not only creates opportunities for conversation but also ensures that the dialogue is directed toward building understanding and appreciating differences. This is reflected in FKAUB's efforts to invite religious leaders from outside the Lely Parish to provide insights and a better understanding of their teachings and beliefs. This approach helps break down the walls of differences and stimulates deeper dialogue. Mr. Ramadi stated in his interview that "FKAUB activities are not only a means to strengthen relationships between believers around the parish but also reinforce believers' perception of the importance of tolerance" (Ramadi, 2023). This indicates that FKAUB not only focuses on forming dialogue but also strives to instill tolerance values into the believers' mindset and actions.

However, it is acknowledged that, as mentioned by Mr. Edy, FKAUB faces challenges in maximizing its efforts to facilitate interfaith dialogue (Edy, 2023). Nevertheless, FKAUB has succeeded in providing insights to Catholic believers that beyond their community, there are brothers and sisters who need to be respected and addressed. This indicates that despite challenges, FKAUB has successfully created a positive impact in expanding the believers' perspectives. Furthermore, FKAUB's success in inviting and involving believers from various religions in joint activities, as emphasized by Mr. Petrus, is a positive indicator that the dialogue facilitated by FKAUB is not only theoretical but also realized in real interactions. The presence of guests from various religions in joint activities creates opportunities for believers to interact directly, feel a sense of togetherness, and mitigate any tensions that may exist. FKAUB is not only an entity known in the Lely Parish but also a primary initiator in facilitating interfaith dialogue. The success of FKAUB in building understanding, stimulating tolerance, and overcoming stereotypical limitations proves that its efforts have a tangible positive impact on shaping harmonious relationships among believers of different faiths in the Lely Parish.

In the third focus on FKAUB's role in promoting religious tolerance, the Interreligious Communication Forum (FKAUB) emerges as a crucial driving force in promoting religious tolerance among the Lely Parish community. Through activities that embrace diversity and open the door to dialogue among believers of different faiths, FKAUB fulfills its role with

dedication to creating an inclusive environment that respects differences. A distinctive feature of FKAUB in promoting religious tolerance is its active involvement in addressing potential religious issues that could lead to conflicts among believers. In interviews with respondents such as Mrs. Nunik, Mr. Ramadi, Mr. Edy, and Mr. Petrus, it was revealed that FKAUB continues to strive to understand and respond to these sensitive issues. Mrs. Nunik, for example, stated that FKAUB actively seeks to address religious issues that often lead to conflicts in the Lely Parish. She said, "when looking at the cooperation of religious leaders, it is good, positive, and it seems to be heading towards conflict resolution" (Nunik, 2023). This effort is a concrete step in creating an environment that is not only physically safe but also emotionally safe for the entire community.

FKAUB realizes that understanding the range of religious tolerance needs to be deeply ingrained among the congregation. This approach is reflected in Mr. Ramadi's statement, emphasizing that FKAUB uses various activities as a means to strengthen relationships among believers around the parish and enhance the congregation's perception of the importance of tolerance. Through a series of activities such as seminars, group discussions, and social events, FKAUB brings believers into direct experiences that shape new attitudes and understanding of religious diversity. Mr. Edy acknowledges that FKAUB is still striving to maximize its potential in facilitating interfaith dialogue, indicating that FKAUB has successfully conveyed to Catholic believers that outside their community, there are brothers and sisters who need to be respected and addressed. In this regard, FKAUB is not only focused on the internal space of the Lely Parish but also opens a window outward to invite believers to recognize and appreciate diversity.

Moreover, FKAUB's role in promoting religious tolerance is also manifested in its ability to communicate effectively with Catholic believers. Mr. Petrus indicates that FKAUB not only provides understanding through activities but also actively communicates with believers to provide better insights into the importance of religious tolerance. This creates an open communication channel between FKAUB and the congregation, ensuring that tolerance values are not just concepts but principles applied in everyday life.

FKAUB's role in promoting religious tolerance in the Lely Parish becomes a cornerstone in the development of believers' faith. Through various activities, addressing sensitive issues, and active efforts to build understanding and communication, FKAUB has become a backbone in shaping the paradigm of religious tolerance in the community. Through its dedication, FKAUB proves that religious diversity is not a source of conflict but a force that unites and enriches the religious life in the Lely Parish.

In the fourth focus on FKAUB's efforts to overcome stereotypes or negative prejudices against Catholic believers, the Interreligious Communication Forum (FKAUB) in the Lely Parish serves not only as a mediator for interfaith dialogue but also as the forefront in overcoming stereotypes and negative prejudices that challenge Catholic believers. Through proactive efforts, FKAUB has successfully created an inclusive space, demonstrating that the diversity of believers is a richness, not a reason for limitation or discrimination.

One of the main strategies implemented by FKAUB is involving Catholic believers in social service activities that include participation from believers of other faiths. Mrs. Nunik's statement indicates that FKAUB has successfully overcome stereotypes by showing that Catholic believers can be good friends to believers of other faiths. Through collaboration in charitable activities, such as social service, FKAUB creates opportunities for Catholic believers to interact and share humanitarian values together with believers of other faiths. Mr. Ramadi notes that while FKAUB has not fully overcome stereotypes or negative prejudices, there has been a change in the community's attitude towards Catholic believers. This shows that FKAUB's efforts are not only symbolic but also have a real impact on the community's perception of Catholic believers. This strategy provides an understanding that Catholic believers are an integral part of the community that deserves respect and recognition.

FKAUB has also succeeded in creating a safe and open space for Catholic believers during the celebration of religious ceremonies. Mr. Ramadi's statement emphasizes that "FKAUB invites believers of other faiths to participate in ensuring security during Christmas or Easter celebrations" (Ramadi, 2023). Involving believers of other faiths in securing Catholic religious events is a concrete step to break down prejudicial walls and create inclusive involvement. Mr. Edy highlights that FKAUB is slowly trying to reduce the negative stigma attached to Catholic believers. By presenting Catholic believers in various activities involving believers from other religions, FKAUB changes the community's perception of Catholic believers. FKAUB not only responds to stereotypes with words but also with tangible actions that show Catholic believers are an active and positive part of building the social and religious environment.

Mr. Petrus states that FKAUB has succeeded in involving believers from various religions in activities in the Lely Parish. This success not only breaks down negative stereotypes but also creates a new understanding for believers of other religions about diversity and the values of Catholic believers. Through direct interaction, the community can clearly see that Catholic believers are an active and positive part of building the social and religious environment.

FKAUB's efforts to overcome stereotypes and negative prejudices against Catholic believers in the Lely Parish are evidence of their active role in nurturing diversity and tolerance. By utilizing concrete activities, FKAUB not only responds to stereotypes with words but also opens space for deeper understanding and active involvement among believers of different faiths. These proactive steps are a crucial foundation in realizing a more inclusive and respectful community in the Lely Parish.

Hans Küng, in his dialog theory, states that religion is not only about theoretical matters but also about living as we experience it; religion concerns attitudes that believe in life, approach to life, and way of life. Most importantly, religion involves the issue of relation or encounter with the "Wholly Other" or "the Holy" (Husin, 2009). Religion becomes a private space for its followers. In this private space, believers must be able to apply all religious values in everyday life. The most effective way is through dialogue. The dialogue mentioned is a

dialogue of love where believers meet and express common values to achieve tolerance in communal life. Every religion surely has common values. These commonalities need to be emphasized in the dialogue. In the awareness of these essential common values, efforts can be made to build public awareness of the moral values that form the basis for fostering tolerance and harmony among believers. Thus, in understanding the essential similarities of religious teachings, according to Hans Küng, it is necessary to objectively understand the fundamental aspects of each religion. This involves efforts to identify the core values that teach love, peace, justice, and other universal virtues. By recognizing the existence of these universal values, society can appreciate that religious diversity is not just about differences but also about unity in the aspiration for goodness and humanity.

Hans Küng also emphasizes a dialogue that respects differences by encouraging believers to see fellow believers of different faiths as coworkers in the spiritual journey towards salvation (Küng, 1980). This can also serve as a means to overcome prejudice and conflicts rooted in religious issues. Thus, in dialog theory, Hans Küng sees religion as a source of values that can create synergistic justice to achieve peace and strengthen the brotherhood of believers. FKAUB seeks to encourage believers, especially in the parish of Maria Diangkat Ke Surga Lely, to build a tolerant attitude by constructing interreligious dialogue. Interreligious dialogue is an effective model of understanding in creating tolerance among believers by emphasizing dialogue among each believer (Taufiq Rahman, 2022). FKAUB seeks to organize activities among believers to instill tolerance values and reduce negative issues and suspicions among believers of different faiths. From the research findings, it is said that FKAUB, with various activities carried out in the Maria Diangkat Ke Surga Lely Church, is able to reduce negative stereotypes of Catholic believers created by believers of other faiths. Thus, dialogue has the function of seeing how the relationship between me and my "religion": the relationship "life" or the relationship "ownership" (Husin, 2003).

In building a dialogue, openness and honesty are required. Hans Küng in his dialog theory emphasizes the importance of openness in a dialogue. An open dialogue is the key to building a deeper understanding among religions and in overcoming distrust and prejudice that often arise due to ignorance (Hans Kung, 1998). In an open dialogue, there is a need for heartfelt honesty to accept the views of other religions without prejudice. Hans Küng asserts the need to construct oneself so as not to question the differences that occur, avoiding the emergence of apathy towards different beliefs. Honest dialogue demands a mutual respect and appreciation for differences, while recognizing the fundamental similarities among various religions (Küng, 1998). The presence of FKAUB becomes a means to facilitate believers, especially in the parish of Maria Diangkat Ke Surga Lely, to promote tolerance values. It is not surprising that with various activities carried out in the Maria Diangkat Ke Surga Lely Church, FKAUB contributes to strengthening faith.

CONCLUSION

In the interview results regarding the contribution of FKAUB in promoting interreligious dialogue in the Lely parish, FKAUB is not only recognized as an entity in the Lely parish but also serves as a driving force in facilitating interfaith dialogue, promoting religious tolerance, and addressing stereotypes or negative prejudices against Catholic believers.

Firstly, the community's awareness of FKAUB has reached a satisfactory level, as expressed by the respondents. Mrs. Nunik stated that FKAUB is well-known, and Mr. Petrus added that FKAUB has become part of the community's familiarity. However, it is worth noting that Mr. Ramadi mentioned some confusion between FKAUB and FKUB. Therefore, it is recommended that FKAUB clarifies its identity to avoid confusion among the community, and this is an important note for improving FKAUB's effectiveness in the future.

The next focus is on FKAUB's role in facilitating interfaith dialogue. From the interview results, it is evident that FKAUB is not only known as a platform for dialogue but also as an initiator of activities that embrace diversity. Mrs. Nunik noted that FKAUB actively facilitates interfaith dialogue through various activities, providing believers with a deeper understanding of religious diversity. FKAUB's success is apparent in its efforts to invite religious leaders from outside to offer insights and better understanding. While some respondents acknowledged challenges in maximizing FKAUB's potential in interfaith dialogue, it is generally depicted that FKAUB has successfully created a safe and open space for interaction among believers of different religions.

Subsequently, FKAUB's role in promoting religious tolerance becomes a key point in the analysis. Through activities that embrace diversity, FKAUB effectively promotes understanding and appreciation of religious differences. From the interviews, it is evident that FKAUB seeks to understand and respond to potential religious issues that could lead to conflicts. FKAUB's success in enriching believers' perspectives on religious diversity is reflected in Mr. Ramadi's statement, emphasizing that FKAUB's activities not only strengthen relationships among believers but also enhance the perception of the importance of tolerance. Despite challenges, FKAUB's efforts in inviting and involving believers from various religions in joint activities indicate that the dialogue it facilitates is not only theoretical but also realized in real interactions.

Moving on to FKAUB's efforts to overcome stereotypes or negative prejudices against Catholic believers, it emerges as the forefront with proactive strategies. By involving Catholic believers in social service activities and creating a safe space during religious ceremonies, FKAUB successfully demonstrates that religious diversity is an enriching wealth, not a reason for limitation. While not fully overcoming stereotypes, there is a noted change in community attitudes towards Catholic believers, aligned with their participation in joint activities involving believers from various religions.

Finally, FKAUB plays a crucial role in the Lely parish, serving not only as a recognized entity but also as a catalyst for interreligious dialogue, promoter of religious tolerance, and mitigator of stereotypes against Catholic believers. The community's awareness of FKAUB is

positive, and its impact on fostering understanding, tolerance, and inclusive interactions is evident through various activities and initiatives. Challenges exist, but FKAUB's proactive strategies contribute to shaping a more harmonious and respectful community in the Lely parish.

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INTERVIEWS

- Ibu Nunik, Ketua WKRI, Paroki Maria Diangkat Ke Surga Lely, Tanggal Wawancara 29 Oktober 2023 pkl. 16.00 s/d 17.00
- Pak Edy, Mantan Ketua Lingkungan St. Lukas, Paroki Maria Diangkat Ke Surga Lely, Tanggal Wawancara 29 Oktober 2023 pkl. 18.00 s/d 19.00.
- Pak Petrus, Sekretaris FKAUB, Paroki Maria Diangkat Ke Surga Lely, Tanggal Wawancara 30 Oktober 2023 pkl. 17.00 s/d 18.00
- Pak Ramadi, Ketua DPP, Paroki Maria Diangkat Ke Surga Lely, Tanggal Wawancara 29 Oktober 2023 pkl. 18.00 s/d 19.00.

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